

Busca Automática	
<p>Date: 28/03/2023 (Author 3)</p>	<p>Base: Scopus String: ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR survey) AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "software engineering") Applied to: título, abstract e palavras-chave Quantity: 652</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR survey) AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "software engineering") Applied to: abstract Quantity: 200</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey") AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "software engineering") Applied to: título, abstract e palavras-chave Quantity: 213</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey") AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "software engineering") Applied to: abstract Quantity: 111</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey") AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management") Applied to: título, abstract e palavras-chave Quantity: 58</p>

Base: Scopus

String: ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey") AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management")

Applied to: abstract

Quantity: 38

Base: Scopus

String: ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR survey) AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management")

Applied to: título, abstract e palavras-chave

Quantity: 105

Base: Scopus

String: ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR survey) AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management")

Applied: abstract

Quantity: 53

Base: Scopus

String: ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey") AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("requirements AND (elicitation OR analysis OR specification OR validation OR management)")

Applied: título, abstract e palavras-chave

Quantity: 0

Base: Scopus

String: ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey") AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("requirements AND (elicitation OR analysis OR specification OR validation OR management)")

	<p>Applied: abstract Quantity: 0</p> <p>Note: Since the string above did not return any results, I made some small changes to the parentheses and quotes, obtaining the following results:</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: (("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey") AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("requirements") " AND " (" elicitation " OR " analysis " OR " specification " OR " validation " OR " management "))</p> <p>Applied to: título, abstract e palavras-chave Quantity: 207</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: (("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey") AND ("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("requirements") " AND " (" elicitation " OR " analysis " OR " specification " OR " validation " OR " management "))R "requirements validation" OR "requirements management")</p> <p>Applied to: abstract Quantity: 117</p> <p>In short, I conclude that the terms “software engineering” and “survey” add multiple roles to the search, so it is necessary to evaluate how these words influence the objective of the study and whether the roles resulting from the inclusion of these terms in the search string are relevant to the purpose of this research.</p>
<p>Data: 30/03/23</p>	<p>Base: Scopus String: (("machine learning" OR "data science" OR "data-driven application" OR "AI application" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR survey) AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management"))</p> <p>Applied to: título, abstract e palavras-chave Quantity: 107</p> <hr style="border-top: 1px dashed yellow;"/> <p>Relevance (10 primeiros artigos)</p>

Escolhidos: 1°, 2°.
Dúvida: 4°, 5°, 10°.
Exclusos: 3°, 6°, 7°, 8°, 9°.

Base: Scopus

String: (("machine learning" OR "data science" OR "data-driven application" OR "AI application" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management"))

Applied to: título, abstract e palavras-chave

Quantity: 58

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 2°, 6°.

Dúvida: 8°, 10°, 9°.

Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 7°.

Base: Scopus

String: (("machine learning" OR "data science" OR "data-driven application" OR "AI application" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "survey") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "software engineering"))

Applied to: título, abstract e palavras-chave

Quantity: 670

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 2°.

Dúvida:

Exclusos: 1°, 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°, 9°, 10°.

Base: Scopus

String: (("machine learning" OR "data science" OR "data-driven application" OR "AI application" OR "artificial intelligence") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "software engineering"))

Applied to: título, abstract e palavras-chave

Quantity: 219

	<p>Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos) Escolhidos: 2°. Dúvida: . Exclusos: 1°, 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°, 9°, 10°.</p>
<p>Data: 31/03/2023</p>	<p>Base: Scopus String:(("machine learning") AND ("requirements egineering") AND ("systematic review")) Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave Quantidade de resultados: 0</p> <p>Base: Scopus String:(("machine learning") AND ("requirements egineering") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review")) Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave Quantidade de resultados: 0</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: (("machine learning") AND ("requirements egineering") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping")) Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave Quantidade de resultados: 0</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: (("machine learning") AND ("requirements egineering") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping")) Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave Quantidade de resultados: 0</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: (("machine learning") AND ("requirements egineering") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey")) Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave Quantidade de resultados: 0</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: (("machine learning") AND ("requirements egineering") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey)) Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave Quantidade de resultados: 0</p> <p>Base: Scopus</p>

	<p>String: (("machine learning") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "elicitation requirements") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))</p> <p>Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave</p> <p>Quantidade de resultados: 0</p>
<p>Data: 05/04/2023</p>	<p>Base: Scopus</p> <p>String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("machine learning" AND "requirements engineering" AND "systematic review")</p> <p>Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave</p> <p>Quantidade de resultados: 7</p> <hr/> <p>Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)</p> <p>Escolhidos: 5°.</p> <p>Dúvida: 2°, 3°, 4°.</p> <p>Exclusos: 1°, 7°, 6°.</p> <p>Base: Scopus</p> <p>String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("machine learning" AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review"))</p> <p>Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave</p> <p>Quantidade de resultados: 25</p> <hr/> <p>Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)</p> <p>Escolhidos: 6°, 7°, 8°, 9°, 10°.</p> <p>Dúvida: 4°, 5°.</p> <p>Exclusos: 1°, 2°, 3°.</p> <p>Base: Scopus</p> <p>String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("machine learning" AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping"))</p> <p>Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave</p> <p>Quantidade de resultados: 34</p> <hr/> <p>Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)</p> <p>Escolhidos: 1°, 4°, 9°.</p> <p>Dúvida: 6°, 7°, 8°.</p> <p>Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 5°, 10°.</p> <p>Base: Scopus</p> <p>String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("machine learning" AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature</p>

mapping"))

Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave

Quantidade de resultados: 34

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 4°, 9°.

Dúvida: 6°, 7°, 8°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 5°, 10°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("machine learning" AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave

Quantidade de resultados: 36

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 4°, 9°.

Dúvida: 6°, 7°, 8°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 5°, 10°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("machine learning" AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR survey))

Aplicado a: título, abstract e palavras-chave

Quantidade de resultados: 46

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 5°, 6°, 10°.

Dúvida: 7°, 8°, 9°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 4°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ("machine learning" AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Applied to: título, abstract e palavras-chave

Quantity: 46

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 5°, 6°, 10°.

Dúvida: 7°, 8°, 9°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 4°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

Applied: título, abstract e palavras-chave

Quantity: 48

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 4°, 6°.

Dúvida: 7°, 8°, 10°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 5°, 9°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence") AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Quantity: 74

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 6°, 7°.

Dúvida: 9°, 10°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 4°, 5°, 8°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science") AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Quantity: 76

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 6°, 7°.

Dúvida: 9°, 10°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 4°, 5°, 8°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science") AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Quantity: 76

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 6°, 7°.

Dúvida: 9°, 10°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 4°, 5°, 8°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science") AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

Quantity: 48

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 4°.

Dúvida: 6°, 7°, 8°, 10°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 5°, 9°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven") AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

Quantity: 54

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 4°.

Dúvida: 6°, 7°, 8°, 10°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 5°, 9°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven") AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Quantity: 93

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 9°, 10°.

Dúvida:

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven application") AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

Quantity: 48

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 4°.

Dúvida: 6°, 7°, 8°, 10°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 5°, 9°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven application") AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Quantity: 76

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 6°, 7°.

Dúvida: 9°, 10°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 4°, 5°, 8°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

Quantity: 54

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 4°.

Dúvida: 6°, 7°, 8°, 10°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 5°, 9°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Quantity: 93

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 9°, 10°.

Dúvida:

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°.

Base: Scopus

String:TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "software engineering") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

Quantity: 233

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 2°.

Dúvida: 8°

Exclusos: 1°, 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 9°, 10°.

Base: Scopus

String:TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "software engineering") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Quantity: 709

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 2°.

Dúvida: 9°

Exclusos: 1°, 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°, 10°.

Base: Scopus

String:TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Quantity: 101

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°.

Dúvida:

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°, 9°, 10°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

Quantity: 57

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 5°.

Dúvida: 7°, 8°, 9°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 10°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

Quantity: 61

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 2°.

Dúvida: 8°, 9°, 10°.

Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Quantity: 120

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 2°.

Dúvida: .

Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°, 9°, 10°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Quantity: 125

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 2°.

Dúvida: .

Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°, 9°, 10°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

Quantity: 63

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 2°, 6°.

Dúvida: 8°, 9°, 10°.

Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 7°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

Quantity: 64

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 2°, 6°.

Dúvida: 8°, 9°, 10°.

Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 7°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Quantity: 126

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 2°.

Dúvida: .

Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°, 9°, 10°

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey" OR survey))

Quantity: 129

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 2°.

Dúvida: .

Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 6°, 7°, 8°, 9°, 10°

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY (("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data science" OR "data driven" OR "AI application") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

Quantity: 65

Análise de relevância (10 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 2°, 6°.

Dúvida: 8°, 9°, 10°.

Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 7°.

<p>Data: 12/04/2023</p>	<p>Base: Scopus String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ((("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data driven") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey")))) Quantity: 65</p> <hr/> <p>Análise de relevância (20 primeiros artigos) Escolhidos: 1°, 2°, 6°, 13°, 15°, 17°, 19°, 20°. Dúvida: 8°, 9°, 10°, 12°, 14°, 16°. Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 7°, 11°, 18°.</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ((("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data-driven") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey")))) Quantity: 65</p> <hr/> <p>Análise de relevância (20 primeiros artigos) [mesmo resultado da pesquisa anterior] Escolhidos: 1°, 2°, 6°, 13°, 15°, 17°, 19°, 20°. Dúvida: 8°, 9°, 10°, 12°, 14°, 16°. Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 7°, 11°, 18°.</p>
<p>Data: 13/04/2023 Análise: 15/04/2023</p>	<p>Base: Scopus String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ((("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data-driven") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey")))) Quantity: 65</p> <hr/> <p>Análise de relevância (20 primeiros artigos) [mesmo resultado da pesquisa anterior] Escolhidos: 1°, 2°, 6°, 13°, 15°, 17°, 19°, 20°. Dúvida: 8°, 9°, 10°, 12°, 14°, 16°. Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 7°, 11°, 18°. Base: Scopus</p>

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ((("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data-driven") AND ("requirements engineering") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey")))

Quantity: 54

Análise de relevância (20 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 4°, 11°, 13°, 14°, 16°, 17°, 18°, 19°.

Dúvida: 6°, 7°, 10°, 12°, 20°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 5°, 8°, 9°, 15°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ((("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data-driven") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey")))

Quantity: 57

Análise de relevância (20 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 5°, 12°, 14°, 15°, 17°, 18°, 19°, 20°.

Dúvida: 7°, 8°, 11°, 13°.

Exclusos: 2°, 3°, 4°, 6°, 9°, 10°, 16°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ((("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data-driven") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey")))

Quantity: 61

Análise de relevância (20 primeiros artigos)

Escolhidos: 1°, 2°, 6°, 13°, 15°, 17°, 19°, 20°.

Dúvida: 8°, 9°, 10°, 12°, 14°, 16°.

Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 7°, 11°, 18°.

Base: Scopus

String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ((("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data-driven") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic

	<p>mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))) Quantity: 63</p> <hr/> <p>Análise de relevância (20 primeiros artigos) [mesmo resultado da pesquisa anterior] Escolhidos: 1°, 2°, 6°, 13°, 15°, 17°, 19°, 20°. Dúvida: 8°, 9°, 10°, 12°, 14°, 16°. Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 7°, 11°, 18°.</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ((("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data-driven") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey")))) Quantity: 64</p> <hr/> <p>Análise de relevância (20 primeiros artigos) [mesmo resultado da pesquisa anterior] Escolhidos: 1°, 2°, 6°, 13°, 15°, 17°, 19°, 20°. Dúvida: 8°, 9°, 10°, 12°, 14°, 16°. Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 7°, 11°, 18°.</p> <p>Base: Scopus String: TITLE-ABS-KEY ((("machine learning" OR "artificial intelligence" OR "data-driven") AND ("requirements engineering" OR "requirements elicitation" OR "requirements analysis" OR "requirements specification" OR "requirements validation" OR "requirements management ") AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey")))) Quantity: 65</p> <hr/> <p>Análise de relevância (20 primeiros artigos) [mesmo resultado da pesquisa anterior] Escolhidos: 1°, 2°, 6°, 13°, 15°, 17°, 19°, 20°. Dúvida: 8°, 9°, 10°, 12°, 14°, 16°. Exclusos: 3°, 4°, 5°, 7°, 11°, 18°.</p>
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Análise de Survey e Literature Survey

[Resultados de Literature Survey](#)

TITLE-ABS-KEY ("machine learning" AND "requirements engineering" AND ("systematic review" OR "systematic literature review" OR "systematic mapping" OR "systematic literature mapping" OR "literature survey"))

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